

THE REASONS WHY STUDENTS SHOULD LEARN FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

The article includes explaining as well as opting for external languages. Moreover, it can verify special features of foreign languages. Particularly, it may help to non-native students and pupils. It not only changes the background of students' knowledge but also tends to create a modern ambiance of brainstorming. In addition to these views, foreign languages are used to assisting in the development of cutting-edge technologies. Furthermore, it can help out exploring new gadgets to the world. For example, several professionals and professors are analyzing and utilizing updated technologies in the sphere of medicine and education. Providing that young learners desire to acquire external languages they could explore original inventions. Finally, external languages can aid in improving social attitudes as well as the economy of several countries.

Key words: special features of foreign languages, non-native students - autonomous, background knowledge of students, the modern ambiance of brainstorming, development of cutting-edge technologies, improvement of social attitude

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Introduction

First of all, every student is inclined to learn various languages, to opt for various careers in the future. Because of globalization, the world's economy is developing not only budget is elevating, but also because social attitudes are being changed by humans. As we know, foreign languages especially, English are becoming the second language these days. Moreover, it can improve the work and career possibilities of individuals. For instance; several studies have shown that learning and speaking external languages will be productive while students communicate with strangers. In addition to this option, bilingual people are smarter, and to be more resistant. Some areas of the brain grow when you learn a foreign language. Furthermore, teenagers keep watch over to enhance their languages which have more opportunities to go abroad and work there. It is the first advantage side of learning foreign languages. As well as we can say that it will be the main reason for developing their business skills.

Foreign language study creates a more positive background of your knowledge not only to improve your system of the brain but also to raise pivotal attitudes toward the people. For example; they may travel around the world and see sightseeing places of the countries. Along with this, they can get more information about that country and qualify their moral behavior of the culture. Additionally, studying a foreign language will help them to meet new and

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interesting foreigners. Dealing with other ethnos enables learners to gain a deeper understanding of their own culture.

Method

The vital reason for inquiring about external languages will elevate listening and speaking skills. It can be pivotal for young learners to get a degree in foreign languages. For instance; students listen to daily conversations from cutting-edge tools, as well as utilizing gadgets, particularly several sites that are scaffolding to assist youngsters will improving their speaking skills. From my point of view, students and pupils should speak in another foreign language with their peers at any time and condition they want. Due to practicing learners will improve their communication skills in front of an audience. Learners can enhance their pronunciation skills which triggers to verify several sounds. So, native speakers might speak clearly and fluently with the help of ameliorating pronunciation. I have read some information based on mastering pronunciation on the website. I desire to obtain authentic information about the topic.

Mastering pronunciation will help learners to memorize words and grammar with greater ease. According to some research, it is significantly harder to memorize words that you have difficulty pronouncing, in other words, the teacher is the person who shows the way as a sign to learners, being good at self-assessment also leads, to consciously avoiding procrastination and increases intrinsic inspiration to move forward. Modern studies have revealed the importance of tackling the sound of language early on.

According to the practice, I have noticed that one is having difficulty differentiating between certain sounds, they recommend that individuals practice and test themselves on those sounds for 20 minutes per day. In addition to these statements, it can be beneficial for our mental health which enhances positivity and critical thinking. For instance, a foreign language is a whole new intricate system of rules, and structures, as well as exciting adventures. Learning an external language means your brain has to cope with complexity as it makes sense of and absorbs new patterns. Moreover, we tend to be aware of the history of that country not only the history of those countries but also, we can know the education and technology system of the country. As our mindset consolidates the meaning, struggling to communicate, we progress key learning skills such as core thinking and problem-solving. Because of watching several podcasts, we tend to improve our knowledge of the problems. It has been shown several consequences of the issue by many professionals.

Discussion

I watched many videos that helped me. By observing the videos, I could get important updates from them. One of them is watching Ali Abdaal. He's one of those people who manages to make incredible big news while being a famous YouTuber and medical guru. As he communicates with some experienced individuals who can achieve high goals, the human need for language is shown. This individual quality, such as the exchanging of ideas with other people, and mutual learning, leads a person to goodness and professional growth. At the same time, some of the interviewees gave important advice to young entrepreneurs to increase self-assessment which makes a learner to be an autonomous learner.

Conclusion

Lastly, learning foreign languages is a source of knowledge related to the personal views and aspirations of each person which increases self-confidence and one can self-assess, it creates great opportunities for a person, especially to

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strengthen the internal motivation of growing students, and it is carried out naturally, mostly based on purpose and target aims.

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